

Original Article

ENHANCING GRADUATE EMPLOYABILITY IN EMERGING ECONOMIES: THE ROLE OF ICT UNIT IN NIGERIAN HIGHER INSTITUTIONS

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Abstract

Graduate employability in emerging economies such as Nigeria remains a critical issue, with a significant number of graduates struggling to secure meaningful employment after completing their higher education. This could be because the skills acquired during higher education often do not align with the demands of the modern job market. The study assessed the role of ICT units of Nigerian higher institutions in enhancing graduate employability. Descriptive survey design was adopted for the study. The population for the study is 120 respondents comprising 100 lecturers and 20 technologists in the College of Education, Michael Okpara University of Agriculture, Umudike Abia State. Simple random sampling technique was used to select 50 respondents comprising 30 lecturers and 20 technologists for the study. A 24-item structured questionnaire validated by two experts and tested for reliability was developed for the study. A five-point Likert rating scale of Strongly Agree, Agree, Undecided, Disagree and Strongly Disagree was used. Data obtained was analysed using mean to answer research questions and t-test to test the null hypotheses at .05 level of significance. Items with mean scores of 3.50 and above were agreed while items with mean scores of 3.49 and below were not agreed. Findings of the study revealed that ICT units contribute immensely to graduate employability in Nigerian higher institutions by equipping students with essential skills for the workplace and ensuring digital skills literacy in student. The study recommended that there should be adequate provision of sufficient funding and financial support by government, corporate entities and individuals. It also recommends that there should be provision of steady electricity, modern infrastructure, equipment, higher internet connectivity as well as the recruitment of proficient technical and administrative personnel.

Keywords: ICT, employability, graduate, Nigerian, higher institutions.

Introduction

In the contemporary global economy, employability has become a pivotal concern for higher education institutions, particularly in emerging economies such as Nigeria. Higher education is fundamental to the construction of a knowledge economy and society as well as a place where skilled labour is produced for societal and global consumption (Adebakin et al., 2015). The increasing unemployment and underemployment rates among graduates underscore the pressing need for educational systems that not only impart theoretical knowledge but also equip students with practical, market-relevant skills. Addressing this challenge is crucial for socio-economic development and national progress. One of the most promising avenues for enhancing graduate employability lies in the strategic deployment of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) within higher education institutions. This study explores the pivotal role of ICT units in Nigerian higher institutions in bridging the gap between academic learning and the demands of the modern job market. Nigeria, as the most populous nation in Africa as well as the most populous black nation in the world, faces significant challenges in aligning its higher education outputs with labor market requirements. The nation's higher institutions which include universities, polytechnics and colleges of education produce a substantial number of graduates annually. However, many of these graduates struggle to secure employment due to a mismatch between their skills and the needs of employers (Agbo, 2015). The resulting high rates of graduate unemployment contribute to broader socio-economic issues, including poverty, insecurity and social instability. Employability could be referred to as a combination of competencies, skills as well as personal attributes, which empower graduates to gain employment and excel in their various professions. It is a multi-

dimensional concept encompassing technical skills, soft skills, and personal attributes such as adaptability and self-efficacy. In the context of Nigerian higher education, the mismatch between these skills and the needs of the labor market has been a persistent challenge (Agbo, 2015). Employability refers to an individual's ability of obtaining initial employment, maintaining employment and obtaining new employment if needed. In a nutshell, employability is the capacity to move independently within the labour market to realize potential through sustainable employment (Olabiyi & Shobowale, 2015). Employability has become an alarming problem globally particularly as the work drifts up to the Fourth Industrial Revolution (UNESCO, 2021). A very useful skill that can promote employability in the 21st century is Information and Communication Technology (ICT). ICT is an acronym which has a wider meaning and is known as Information and Communication Technology representing the use of different technologies and networks that can electronically be accessed, stored, transmitted and retrieved at any point in time (Tonwe, 2022). ICT encompasses all technologies used for handling telecommunications, broadcasting media, intelligent building management systems, audiovisual processing, and transmission systems, and network-based control and monitoring functions. In recent years, ICT has profoundly impacted various sectors, including education, healthcare, business, and governance. This literature review explores the multifaceted role of ICT, highlighting its significance, applications, and challenges across different domains. The evolution of ICT can be traced back to the invention of the telegraph and the telephone in the 19th century. However, significant advancements occurred in the late 20th and early 21st centuries with the advent of the internet, mobile communications, and digital

computing. The continuous innovation in ICT has led to the development of new technologies such as cloud computing, big data analytics, and the Internet of Things (IoT), further enhancing its capabilities and applications (Brock, 2016). Computers and their peripherals such as printers, software, scanners, and projectors are often utilized in teaching and learning. Indeed, ICT represents a paradigm change in how humans use computers and the internet to interpret information. Similarly, Oyedokun and Adeolu-Akande (2022) posited that ICT has changed the model of information sharing from static to dynamic. Oyedokun and Adeolu-Akande further noted that the integration of ICT into higher education allows students to access more sophisticated and broad fields of study in order to improve their analytical skills. Due to its dynamic, interactive and interesting content, ICT has improved teaching and learning. ICT units in Nigerian higher institutions could be a pivotal focus to graduate employability in Nigeria. They serve as the backbone for integrating technology into the educational framework, thereby enhancing the learning experience and preparing students for the digital economy (Olaniyi, 2016). These units are typically responsible for maintaining ICT infrastructure, supporting e-learning initiatives, and providing training in digital skills.

The Role of ICT in Modern Education

Globally, ICT has revolutionized education by transforming traditional pedagogical methods and expanding access to learning resources. In the Nigerian context, the adoption of ICT in higher education has been gradual but impactful, offering significant opportunities to enhance educational outcomes and employability.

One of the primary roles of ICT units is to bridge the skill gap between academic training and industry requirements. By providing students with access to various digital tools and platforms, ICT units help

cultivate both technical and soft skills essential for the modern workforce. Proficiency in software applications, data analysis, and coding can significantly enhance a graduate's employability (Eze, Adu, & Salako, 2018). Additionally, the use of collaborative tools and online communication platforms fosters critical soft skills such as teamwork, communication, and problem-solving (Okafor, 2019). Moreover, ICT units help integrate industry-specific training and certifications into academic programs. For example, partnerships with tech companies can offer students opportunities to gain certifications in relevant software and technologies, thereby enhancing their employability (Okafor, 2019). The advent of e-learning and blended learning models has been a game-changer in higher education. ICT units facilitate these learning models by providing the necessary infrastructure and technical support. Blended learning, which combines online and face-to-face instruction, offers a flexible and effective learning approach, catering to diverse student needs and learning styles (Adeoye, 2020). ICT units also play a crucial role in fostering research and innovation within higher institutions. Advanced ICT tools and software enable sophisticated data analysis, enhance research collaboration, and streamline the dissemination of research findings. By supporting a robust research environment, ICT units contribute to academic excellence and innovation, which are key drivers of economic development and employability (Okoro, 2017). Moreover, ICT units help bridge the gap between students and potential employers. These platforms not only facilitate job placements but also provide valuable insights into industry trends and employer expectations (Ajadi, 2020). Through online recruitment platforms, virtual job fairs, and professional networking sites, students can connect

with industry professionals, access job listings, and apply for internships and employment opportunities.

Challenges of ICT Units in Nigerian Higher Institutions

Despite the benefits, ICT units in Nigerian higher education faces several challenges. These include inadequate infrastructure, limited funding, lack of trained personnel, and issues related to the digital divide (Bello, 2019). Many institutions struggle with outdated equipment, unreliable internet connectivity, and insufficient technical support. Addressing these challenges requires substantial investment and strategic planning. Effective ICT integration requires strong policy and institutional support. Government policies that promote ICT in education, along with adequate funding and training programs, are essential. Therefore, this study seeks to explore the specific roles ICT units play, the challenges they face, and the strategies that can be implemented to maximize their impact on graduate employability.

Statement of the Problem

One of the specific goals of education in Nigeria is to promote functional education for skill acquisition, job creation and poverty reduction and also to promote Information and Communication Technology capability at all levels (Federal Republic of Nigeria, 2013). This implies that the country's education is channeled towards inculcating skills and competencies in its citizens, ensure the creation of jobs which includes reducing unemployment as well as minimizing poverty rate in the country. Further, ICT is to be promoted at all levels including the education sector. Unfortunately, graduate employability in emerging economies such as Nigeria remains a critical issue, with a significant number of graduates struggling to secure meaningful employment after completing their higher education. According to the National Bureau of Statistics (2020), Nigeria's unemployment rate has been on a

steady rise, with youth unemployment reaching alarming levels. Higher education institutions in Nigeria face significant challenges in preparing graduates for the rapidly changing and technology-driven labor market. Traditional pedagogical methods, which are heavily reliant on theoretical knowledge, have proven insufficient in equipping students with the practical and digital skills required by employers.

The core problem this research addresses is the lack of effective integration and utilization of ICT units in Nigerian higher institutions to enhance graduates' employability. Despite the recognition of ICT's importance, there is a significant gap in understanding how these units can be optimized to bridge the skills gap between academia and the labor market. If this problem is not addressed, most graduates may end up not acquiring the relevant employability skills needed for the world of work. This study therefore seeks to explore the specific roles ICT units play, the challenges they face, and the strategies that can be implemented to maximize their impact on graduate employability.

Purpose of the Study

The general purpose of this study is to identify the role of ICT units of Nigerian higher institutions in enhancing graduate employability. Specifically, the study seeks to;

1. Assess the functions of ICT units in enhancing graduate employability in Nigerian higher institutions.
2. Identify the key challenges faced by ICT units in enhancing graduate employability in Nigerian higher institutions.
3. Identify strategies for optimizing ICT units to improve graduate employability for the labour market.

Research Questions

1. What are the functions of ICT units in enhancing graduate employability in Nigerian higher institutions?
2. What are the key challenges faced by ICT units in enhancing graduate employability in Nigerian higher institutions?
3. What are the strategies for optimizing ICT units to improve graduate employability for the labor market?

Hypotheses

Ho₁: There is no significant difference between the mean responses of lecturers and technologists on the functions of ICT units in enhancing graduate employability in Nigerian higher institutions.

Ho₂: There is no significant difference between the mean responses of lecturers and technologists on the key challenges faced by ICT units in enhancing graduate employability in Nigerian higher institutions.

Ho₃: There is no significant difference between the mean responses of lecturers and technologists on the strategies for optimizing ICT units to improve graduate employability for the labour market.

Methodology

Descriptive survey design was adopted for the study. The population for the study is 120 respondents comprising 100 lecturers and 20 technologists in the College of Education, Michael Okpara University of Agriculture, Umudike Abia State. Simple random sampling technique was used to select 50

respondents comprising 30 lecturers and 20 technologists for the study. A 24-item structured questionnaire validated by two experts and tested for reliability was developed for the study. The questionnaire had two sections: A and B; section A elicited the demographic information of the respondents and section B had items based on the research questions. The instrument was structured by the researchers on a five-point Likert scale of Strongly Agree (SA) - 5, Agree (A) – 4, Undecided (U) – 3, Disagree (D) -2, and Strongly Disagree (SD) – 1. Google forms was used to administer the questionnaire to the respondents so as to reduce cost. The researchers recorded hundred percent (98%) response rate as the responses were automatically retrieved online. Data obtained was analysed using mean to answer research questions and t-test to test the null hypotheses at .05 level of significance. The decision rule for the research questions was a cut-off point of 3.50. The hypotheses were accepted when the computed value of t (t-calculated) at p<0.05 level of significance at an obtained degree of freedom is less than the t-table value, otherwise it was rejected. The data obtained from the study was analysed using the statistical package for social sciences (SPSS).

Results

Research Question One

What are the functions of ICT units in enhancing graduate employability in Nigerian higher institutions?

Table 1: Mean responses of lecturers and technologists on the functions of ICT units in enhancing graduate employability in Nigerian Higher Institutions.

S/N	Item Statements	Lecturers N ₁ =30		Technologists N ₂ = 20		Decision
		\bar{x}_1	SD ₁	\bar{x}_2	SD ₂	
1	ICT units facilitate learning models and support e-learning initiatives by providing necessary infrastructure and technical support.	4.333	.787	4.175	.826	Agree
2	ICT units provide training in digital skills for students	4.158	.841	4.263	.856	Agree
3	ICT units integrate technology into the educational framework.	4.140	.934	3.895	.920	Agree
4	ICT units enhance learning experiences and prepare	3.983	.896	3.930	.842	Agree

	students for the digital economy.					
5	ICT units promotes digital literacy in students	4.421	.865	4.421	.823	Agree
6	ICT units equips students with essential skills for the contemporary workplace.	4.105	.699	4.193	.611	Agree
7	ICT units provide students with access to various digital tools and platforms.	4.263	.877	4.158	.902	Agree
8	ICT units help integrate industry-specific training and certifications into academic programmes.	4.193	.718	4.035	.778	Agree
9	ICT units foster research and innovation within higher institutions.	4.246	.851	3.983	.916	Agree
10	ICT units help bridge the gap between students and potential employers through online recruitment platforms, virtual job fairs and professional networking sites.	4.263	.720	4.193	.789	Agree
Grand Mean/Standard Deviation		4.211	0.819	4.125	0.826	Agree

Data presented in Table 1 shows that all the 10 items have the mean scores of lecturers and technologists above the cut-off point of 3.50. This shows that all the items were accepted by the respondents as functions of ICT units in enhancing graduate employability in Nigerian higher institutions.

Table 2: Mean responses of lecturers and technologists on the challenges faced by ict units in enhancing graduate employability in Nigerian Higher Institutions.

S/N o	Item Statements	Lecturers N ₁ =30		Technologists N ₂ = 20		Decision
		\bar{X}_1	SD ₁	\bar{X}_2	SD ₂	
11	Lack of modern infrastructure.	4.351	.744	4.281	.796	Agree
12	Insufficient funding and mismanagement of available funds.	4.474	.782	4.333	.809	Agree
13	Lack of trained and proficient personnel.	4.754	.510	4.526	.735	Agree
14	Insufficient technical support.	4.368	.587	4.263	.720	Agree
15	Lack of effective administration strategies by management.	4.719	.526	4.509	.735	Agree
16	Use of outdated equipment and unreliable internet connectivity.	4.228	.756	4.175	.805	Agree
17	Lack of stable power supply.	4.649	.551	4.439	.732	Agree
18	Incessant strikes by professional associations	4.368	.587	4.246	.714	Agree
Grand Mean/Standard Deviation		4.489	0.630	4.347	0.756	Agree

Data presented in Table 2 shows that all the 8 items have the mean scores of lecturers and technologists above the cut-off point of 3.50. This shows that all the items were accepted by the respondents as key challenges faced by ICT units in enhancing graduate employability in Nigerian higher institutions.

Table 3: Mean responses of lecturers and technologists on the strategies for optimizing ICT units to improve graduate employability for the labour market.

S/N	Item Statements	Lecturers	Technologists	Decision
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Research Question Two

What are the key challenges faced by ICT units in enhancing graduate employability in Nigerian higher institutions?

Research Question Three

What are the strategies for optimizing ICT units to improve graduate employability for the labor market?

		N ₁ =30		N ₂ = 20		
		\bar{X}_1	SD ₁	\bar{X}_2	SD ₂	
19	Provision of sufficient funding and financial support by government, corporate entities and individuals.	4.561	.682	4.404	.799	Agree
20	Ensure regular in-service training of technical and administrative personnel.	4.404	.623	4.298	.731	Agree
21	Recruitment of proficient technical and administrative personnel.	4.579	.625	4.368	.770	Agree
22	Use of effective administrative strategies by management of ICT units.	4.719	.526	4.421	.731	Agree
23	Provision of modern infrastructure, equipment and higher internet connectivity.	4.404	.563	4.263	.669	Agree
24	Provision of stable power supply.	4.684	.540	4.474	.630	Agree
Grand Mean/Standard Deviation		4.559	0.593	4.371	0.722	Agree

Data presented in Table 3 shows that all the 6 items have the mean scores of lecturers and technologists above the cut-off point of 3.50. This shows that all the items were accepted by the respondents as strategies for optimizing ICT units to improve graduate employability for the labor market.

Table 4: Summary of t-Test analysis of mean responses of lecturers and technologists on the functions of ICT units in enhancing graduate employability in Nigerian Higher Institutions.

Groups	No	Mean	Standard Deviation	Level of Sig.	df	t-cal	t-tab	Decision
Lecturers	30	4.211	0.819	0.05	48	0.36	1.68	Accept
Technologists	20	4.125	0.826					

The t-test analysis presented in Table 4 shows that the calculated value of t (t-cal) is 0.36 at 48 degree of freedom and at 0.05 level of significance is less than the table value (t-tab) which is 1.68. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted. This signifies that there is no significant difference between the mean responses of lecturers and technologists on the

Hypothesis One

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between the mean responses of lecturers and technologists on the functions of ICT units in enhancing graduate employability in Nigerian higher institutions.

functions of ICT units in enhancing graduate employability in Nigerian higher institutions.

Hypothesis Two

H₀₂: There is no significant difference between the mean responses of lecturers and technologists on the key challenges faced by ICT units in enhancing graduate employability in Nigerian higher institutions.

Table 5: Summary of t-Test analysis of mean responses of lecturers and technologists on the key challenges faced by ICT units in enhancing graduate employability in Nigerian Higher Institutions.

Groups	No	Mean	Standard Deviation	Level of Sig.	Df	t-cal	t-tab	Decision
Lecturers	30	4.489	0.630	0.05	48	0.69	1.68	Accept
Technologists	20	4.347	0.756					

The t-test analysis presented in Table 6 shows that the calculated value of t (t-cal) is 0.69 at 48 degree of freedom and at 0.05 level of significance is less than the table value (t-tab) which is 1.68. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted. This signifies that there is no significant difference between the mean responses of lecturers and technologists on the key

Table 6: Summary of t-Test analysis of mean responses of lecturers and technologists on the strategies for optimizing ICT units to improve graduate employability for the labour market.

Groups	No	Mean	Standard Deviation	Level of Sig.	df	t-cal	t-tab	Decision
Lecturers	30	4.559	0.593	0.05	48	0.96	1.68	Accept
Technologists	20	4.371	0.722					

The t-test analysis presented in Table 6 shows that the calculated value of t (t-cal) is 0.96 at 48 degree of freedom and at 0.05 level of significance is less than the table value (t-tab) which is 1.68. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted. This signifies that there is no significant difference between the mean responses of lecturers and technologies on strategies for optimizing ICT units to improve graduate employability for the labour market.

Findings and Discussion

Table one shows that the mean scores of all the 10 items have the mean scores of lecturers and technologists above the cut-off point of 3.50 on the five point Likert scale. Also, it further showed that all the items were accepted by the respondents as functions of ICT units in enhancing graduate employability in Nigerian higher institutions. This finding is in agreement with the findings of Okoro (2017) who stated that ICT units contribute to academic excellence and innovation, which are key drivers of economic development and employability. This emphasises the importance of ICT units in higher institutions in Nigeria. Also, the t-test analysis presented in Table 4 shows that the calculated value of t (t-cal) is 0.36 at 48 degree of freedom and at 0.05 level of significance is less than the table value (t-tab) which is 1.68. Therefore, the null hypothesis

challenges faced by ICT units in enhancing graduate employability in Nigerian higher institutions.

Hypothesis Three

H₀: There is no significant difference between the mean responses of lecturers and technologists on the strategies for optimizing ICT units to improve graduate employability for the labour market.

is accepted. This signifies that there is no significant difference between the mean responses of lecturers and technologists on the functions of ICT units in enhancing graduate employability in Nigerian higher institutions. The findings from Table two revealed that all the 8 items have the mean scores of lecturers and technologists above the cut-off point of 3.50. This shows that all the items were accepted by the respondents as challenges faced by ICT units in enhancing graduate employability in Nigerian higher institutions. In line with this finding, Bello (2019) posits that these challenges faced by ICT units in Nigerian higher institutions include inadequate infrastructure, limited funding, lack of trained personnel, and issues related to the digital divide. Additionally, the t-test analysis presented in Table 6 shows that the calculated value of t (t-cal) is 0.69 at 48 degree of freedom and at 0.05 level of significance is less than the table value (t-tab) which is 1.68. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted. This signifies that there is no significant difference between the mean responses of lecturers and technologists on the key challenges faced by ICT units in enhancing graduate employability in Nigerian higher institutions. Table three revealed that provision of sufficient funding and financial support by government, corporate entities and

individuals, ensuring regular in-service training of technical and administrative personnel and provision of stable electricity, modern infrastructure, equipment and higher internet connectivity among others are some of the strategies for optimizing ICT units to improve graduate employability for the labour market. Supporting this finding was Ajadi (2020) who stated that effective ICT integration requires strong policy and institutional support for effective service delivery. Furthermore, the t-test analysis presented in Table 6 shows that the calculated value of t (t-cal) is 0.96 at 48 degree of freedom and at 0.05 level of significance is less than the table value (t-tab) which is 1.68. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted. This signifies that there is no significant difference between the mean responses of lecturers and technologies on strategies for optimizing ICT units to improve graduate employability for the labour market.

Conclusion

The role of ICT units in enhancing graduates' employability in Nigerian higher institutions is indispensable. By fostering digital literacy, supporting innovative learning models, facilitating research, and connecting students to the job market, ICT units help bridge the gap between academic training and industry needs. As Nigeria continues to navigate the complexities of the global economy, leveraging ICT in education will be crucial in preparing graduates to thrive in the digital age. This study explored these dynamics in detail, providing insights and recommendations to optimize the impact of ICT in enhancing graduate employability.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are made;

1. Government should provide adequate funding for the provision of ICT units in Higher Institutions.

2. Institutions should ensure regular in-service training of technical and administrative personnel.
3. Government and Nigerian higher institutions should recruit proficient technical and administrative personnel to ensure adequate productivity and quality service delivery.
4. Government should ensure provision of steady electricity, modern infrastructure, equipment and higher internet connectivity for ICT units to enhance service delivery towards graduate employability.
5. Institutional managements should employ effective and relevant administrative strategies in ICT units.

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